

ELASTIC BEHAVIOUR OF PARTICULATE NITRIDE-NITRIDE OR BORIDE-NITRIDE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY : Hight density refractory AlN-TiN, AlN-TiB₂ and TiN-TiB₂ composites, as well as the monolithic ceramics : i.e. aluminium nitride AlN, titanium nitride TiN and titanium diboride TiB₂ were elaborated by Hot Isostatic Pressing.

Measurements of the Young's and Shear moduli of these polycrystalline materials were performed at room temperature by an ultrasonic pulse-echo method.

First, the study aim was the elastic properties examination of composites at room temperature.

Second, the experimental values obtained on various compositions were compared to predict values based on semi-empirical equations proposed in literature for a two-phased ceramic.

Correlations between the theoretical and the experimental moduli are discussed.

KEYWORDS : Elastic properties, Hot Isostatic Pressing, Particulate biphased ceramics, Titanium nitride, Aluminium nitride, Titanium diboride.

INTRODUCTION

Hot Isostatic Pressing has been now widely applied on various powders to produce dense ceramics of high properties, without the use of sintering additive.

Among them, titanium nitride and titanium diboride based ceramics are suitable for electrical discharge machining. The high hardness, melting point and wettability by molten aluminium of titanium diboride have led to various applications as evaporation boats for metal melting, wear parts, cathodes or cutting tools.

Moreover, titanium nitride affords an interest for nuclear applications and aluminium nitride is widely used for electronic devices.

Such interesting properties have attracted the interest of the scientific community : composites with an electrically conductive secondary phase, i.e. TiB₂ or TiN, have been developed for some specific applications such as heaters, cutting tools and wear-resistant components ; AlN-TiB₂ particulate composites are industrially used for protection against armor piercing.

This paper deals with elastic properties of three binary systems : TiN-TiB₂, AlN-TiB₂, AlN-TiN. The investigation has been conducted over a wide composition range ; the experimental results are compared and discussed with calculated values obtained from models proposed in literature for multiphased materials.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Powders characteristics

The powders characteristics are given in Table 1.

Table 1 : Characteristics of the powders

Powder	Chemical analysis (wt %)								Mean grain diameter (μm)	Specific area (m ² /g)
	Ti	B	Al	N	O	C	Fe	other metals		
TiB ₂	>67.5	31.6	-	0.03	0.3	0.12	0.1	<0.1	5.8	<0.6
AlN	-	-	>64.5	33.4	1	0.04	0.0045	<0.1	2.6	3.5
TiN	77.16	-	-	22.1	0.6	0.09	0.045	<0.1	3.6	1.8

2.2. Process

The powders were cold isostically pressed under 200 MPa and the green moulded material was introduced inside a silica container. An inert BN layer, which acts as a diffusion barrier, was necessary to prevent chemical reactions between the capsule and the component. Degassing was carried below 600°C, in vacuum (10⁻³ Pa), for 10 hours.

The HIP parameters (temperature and pressure) were defined by taking into account the plastic deformation of the container. The materials were sintered either at 1700°C (AlN-TiN) or at 1950°C (TiN-TiB₂ and AlN-TiB₂). The maximum pressure applied for 90 minutes was 195 MPa. Cylinders were obtained and machined into bars of the desired size (4x4x25 mm³) for ultrasonic measurements.

2.3. Materials characterization

The density of the sintered materials was determined by hydrostatic and geometrical measurements with an accuracy of 0.1 %.

Diffraction patterns were obtained with a Siemens D5000 diffractometer equipped with a back monochromater. The cell parameters were refined with a least squares program involving corrections of the zero diffractometer shift.

Measurements of elastic moduli have been performed at room temperature by the way of an ultrasonic pulse-echo technique. Measurements were made at 15 MHz for longitudinal waves and 10 MHz for shear waves by reflexion between two parallel faces along two directions perpendicular to the bar axis, in order to verify isotropy.

A pulse-echo overlap method was used to measure the time between two successive echoes and the velocities of longitudinal wave V_L and of shear wave V_T were obtained ^[1] by using Eqns 1-4 :

$$V_L = \frac{2e}{t_L} \text{ and } V_T = \frac{2e}{t_T} \quad (1)$$

where e is sample thickness, t_L and t_T are the measured times for longitudinal and shear waves respectively.

Young's and shear moduli (E and G) and Poisson's ratio (ν) are then calculated by :

$$E = d \frac{3V_L^2 - 4V_T^2}{\frac{V_L^2}{V_T^2} - 1} \quad (2)$$

$$G = d V_T^2 \quad (3)$$

where d is density.

$$\nu = \frac{V_L^2 - 2V_T^2}{2(V_L^2 - V_T^2)} \quad (4)$$

Measurements were performed with precisions of 0.5 % for t , 0.5 % for e and 0.1 % for d . Then, the accuracy on the determination of the elastic parameters are 5 % for E , 2 % for G and 15 % for ν .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Experimental results

Near fully dense materials (monolithic and composites ; relative density $\geq 99\%$) were obtained by Hot Isostatic Pressing without grain coarsening.

For composite materials, an homogeneous distribution of the two phases is noticed by optical micrography. Besides, no reaction is observed between nitride-nitride or nitride-boride powders during HIPing. This is confirmed by thermodynamic calculations.

Moreover, the densification treatment does not induce a deviation from stoichiometry, as verified by XRD analysis, even for titanium nitride which admits a large unstoichiometric range.

Elastic constants of monolithic nitrides and boride as well as of composite ceramics have been measured. Young's and shear moduli of the pure ceramics are given in Table 2.

Table 2 : Young's and shear moduli measured for pure ceramics

	E (GPa)	G (GPa)
TiN	470 ± 13	195 ± 4
TiB₂	568 ± 28	256 ± 5
AlN	318 ± 16	128 ± 3

The evolutions with composition of Young's and shear moduli, as well as Poisson's ratio of composite materials are shown on Fig. 1.

The variation of E and G versus volumic concentration x of TiB_2 or TiN can be fitted by linear equations (Eqns 5-10) ; r is correlation coefficient.

$$E_{TiN-TiB_2} \text{ (GPa)} = 471 + 1.0x \quad r = 0.996 \quad (5)$$

$$G_{TiN-TiB_2} \text{ (GPa)} = 194 + 0.6x \quad r = 0.997 \quad (6)$$

$$E_{AlN-TiB_2} \text{ (GPa)} = 296 + 2.5x \quad r = 0.990 \quad (7)$$

$$G_{\text{AlN-TiB}_2} \text{ (GPa)} = 117 + 1.2x \quad r = 0.986 \quad (8)$$

$$E_{\text{AlN-TiN}} \text{ (GPa)} = 325 + 1.5x \quad r = 0.992 \quad (9)$$

$$E_{\text{AlN-TiN}} \text{ (GPa)} = 130 + 0.7x \quad r = 0.991 \quad (10)$$

a

b

c

Fig. 1 : Evolution of Young's and shear moduli with composition (left)
Evolution of Poisson's ratio with composition (right)

a : TiN-TiB₂

b : AlN-TiB₂

c : AlN-TiN

3.2. Discussion

The values given in the literature for the elastic moduli of pure polycrystalline monolithic materials (AlN, TiN and TiB₂), vary considerably (Table 3).

Table 3 : Young's moduli of pure ceramics

	E (GPa)	References
TiN	402-436	2, 3
TiB₂	499-543	4-8
AlN	307-321	9, 10

The main cause of such discrepancy is porosity : i.e. size, location and shape. Compared to these literature data, the values of Table 2 are higher which may be attributed to the low porosity of the hipped samples ^[3].

For polycrystalline solids, the dependence of Young's moduli on porosity has been extensively studied by numerous authors in literature ^[11-19] in order to predict theoretical limits for full dense materials.

Among all the relations proposed to correlate elastic properties to porosity, two empirical equations of Budiansky ^[20] or MacKenzie ^[12] (Eqns 11 and 12) have been derived by considering a negligible evolution of Poisson's ratio ν with porosity ^[20-22] :

$$\frac{E}{E_0} = 1 - \frac{3(9 + 5\nu)(1 - \nu)}{2(7 - 5\nu)} P \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{E}{E_0} = 1 - \frac{15(1 - \nu)}{7 - 5\nu} P - 2 \frac{4 - 5\nu}{7 - 5\nu} P^2 \quad (12)$$

E_0 being the Young's modulus of composites without porosity.

The application of equation 11 or 12 to our results has shown that the correction does not exceed 3%, which is inferior to the experimental error of 5% (Table 4).

Table 4 : Comparison between the as-measured E values and the E_0 values corrected versus porosity.

	E (GPa) (experimental)	E_0 (GPa)
TiN	470 ± 13	473
TiB₂	568 ± 28	584
AlN	318 ± 16	321

Rigorously, composite properties are not a simple linear combination of the constituent properties. In order to predict the effective elastic moduli of a multiphased material as a function of the volume fraction of the constituents, the composite is described as a mixture of two isotropic and homogeneous monolithic phases.

It is well known ^[23-25] that grains orientation within hot pressed polycrystalline materials is close to random. This is verified in the present case : ultrasonic velocities were the same whatever the orientation of measurements axis.

Then, the composites have been modelled as biphased homogeneous and isotropic materials.

Among a lot of theoretical approaches for the prediction of elastic properties of biphased materials, we have chosen the simplest ones.

Voigt (assuming strain continuity) and Reuss (assuming stress continuity) relations give upper bound G_V and lower one G_R for the prediction of G ^[24-25] (Eqns 13 and 14) :

$$G_V = v_1 G_1 + v_2 G_2 \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{1}{G_R} = \frac{v_1}{G_1} + \frac{v_2}{G_2} \quad (14)$$

where G_i and v_i represent the shear modulus and the fractional volume of phase i respectively.

Moreover, the Hashin and Shtrikman analysis, based on variational principles of elasticity leads to a rather narrow domain of prediction between lower and upper bounds for G (HS+, HS-) ^[26] (Eqns 15 and 16) :

$$G_{HS-} = G_m + \frac{v_r}{\frac{1}{G_r - G_m} + \frac{6(K_m + 2G_m)v_m}{5G_m(3K_m + 4G_m)}} \quad (15)$$

$$G_{HS+} = G_r + \frac{v_m}{\frac{1}{G_m - G_r} + \frac{6(K_r + 2G_r)v_r}{5G_r(3K_r + 4G_r)}} \quad (16)$$

where suffixes m and r represent the matrix and the reinforcing phase respectively and K_i are the bulk moduli.

These bounds have been calculated by taking G as the shear moduli of pure ceramics given in Table 2.

The experimental data (\blacklozenge) and theoretical values calculated from the Voigt, Reuss, Hashin and Shtrikman relations are in good agreement (Fig. 2).

a

b

c

Fig. 2 : Comparison between experimental values and Voigt and Reuss bounds (left)
Comparison between experimental values and Hashin and Shtrikman bounds (right)

a : TiN-TiB₂
b : AlN-TiB₂
c : AlN-TiN

CONCLUSION

Boride-nitride composites constitute a family of materials able to perform under a wide variety of service conditions. Besides the intrinsic feature of each material, the composite properties are strongly influenced by the starting composition, the microstructure and the processing parameters. Consequently, literature data are scattered [27-28].

The use of HIP process provides a total densification of powders without sintering additive and is the best technique to reach the closest elastic parameters values of zero porosity materials.

On the other way, a great number of theoretical approaches to predict the elastic constant of two-phased composites as a function of volume fraction of secondary phase has been analysed. The calculated values of elastic constants have been compared to the experimental ones.

Though a very few porosity remains, a rather good agreement is found between theoretical data and experimental values which shows that the two phases of the composite materials are well bonded and homogeneously distributed.

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REFERENCES

- [1] E.P. Papadakis, `` Practical aspects of research with ultrasonic waves '', *Int. J. Nondestruct. Test.*, Vol. 1, No. 4, 1970, pp. 383-399.
- [2] T. Graziani, A. Bellosi, `` Densification and characteristics of TiN ceramics '', *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, Vol. 14, 1995, pp. 1078-1081.
- [3] M. Desmanson-Brut, J.C. Glandus, J. Montintin, F. Valin, M. Boncoeur, `` Elastic moduli - Porosity relations in transition metal nitrides : TiN, ZrN, HfN and TaN '', *Ceramics Today, Tomorrow's Ceramics*, Ed. P. Vincenzini, Elsevier Science Publishers B.V, 1991, pp. 1713-1720.
- [4] H. R. Baumgartner, R. A. Steiger, `` Sintering and properties of titanium diboride made from powder synthesized in a plasma-arc heater '', *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 67, No. 3, 1984, pp. 207-212.
- [5] V. J. Tennery, C. B. Finch, C. S. Yust, G. W. Clark, `` Structure-property correlations for TiB₂-based ceramics densified using active liquid metals '', *Proc. 1st Int. Conf. Sci. Hard Mater.*, Jackson, USA, Ed. J. Viswanadham, R. K. Rowcliffe, D. J. Gurland, Plenum Press, New-York, 1981, pp. 891-909.
- [6] M. K. Ferber, P. F. Becher, C. B. Finch, `` Effect of microstructure on the properties of TiB₂ ceramics '', *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 66, No. 1, 1983, pp. C2-C4.

- [7] M. H. Manghnani, E. S. Fisher, F. Y. Li, D. E. Grady, "The elastic moduli of TiB₂", *Ceram. Trans.*, Vol. 38, 1994, pp. 771-785.
- [8] D. E. Wiley, W. R. Manning, O. Hunter Jr, "Elastic properties of polycrystalline TiB₂, ZrB₂ and HfB₂ from room temperature to 1300 K", *Less-Common Metals*, Vol. 18, 1969, pp. 149-157.
- [9] K. Hunold, "Properties and microstructure of hot isostatic pressed AlN and hexagonal BN", *Proc. Int. Conf. on HIP*, Lulea, Sweden, 1987, pp. 345-351.
- [10] A. K. Knudsen, "Aluminium nitride", *Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull.*, Vol. 74, No. 6, 1995, pp. 97-100.
- [11] W.R. Manning, O. Hunter, B.R. Powell, "Elastic properties of polycrystalline yttrium oxide, dysprosium oxide, holmium oxide and erbium oxide : room temperature measurements", *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 52, No. 8, 1969, pp. 436-442.
- [12] K.K. Phani, S.K. Niyoki, "Young's modulus of porous brittle solids", *J. Mater. Sci.*, Vol. 22, 1987, pp. 257-263.
- [13] E.A. Dean, J.A. Lopez, "Empirical dependence of elastic moduli on porosity for ceramic materials", *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 66, 1983, pp. 366-370.
- [14] R.W. Rice, "Comment on "porosity dependence of fracture mechanical properties of reaction sintered Si₃N₄""", *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, Vol. 7, 1988, pp. 1257-1268.
- [15] J.C. Wang, "Young's modulus of porous materials", *J. Mater. Sci.*, Vol. 19, 1984, pp. 801-808.
- [16] R.E. Fryxell, B.A. Chandler, "Creep, strength, expansion and elastic moduli of sintered BeO as a function of grain size, porosity and grain orientation", *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 47, No. 6, 1964, pp. 283-291.
- [17] R.M. Spriggs, "Expression for effect of porosity on elastic modulus of polycrystalline refractory material, particularly aluminium oxide", *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 44, 1961, pp. 628-629.
- [18] D.P.H. Hasselman, "Porosity dependence of the elastic moduli of polycrystalline refractory materials", *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 45, 1962, pp. 452-453.
- [19] R.B. Martin, R.R. Haynes, "Confirmation of theoretical relation between stiffness and porosity in ceramics", *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 54, No. 8, 1971, pp. 410-411.
- [20] B. Budiandsky, "On the elastic moduli of some heterogeneous materials", *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol. 13, 1965, pp. 223-227.
- [21] Z. Hashin, "Elastic moduli of heterogeneous materials", *J. Appl. Mech.*, Vol. 29, No. 1, 1962, pp. 143-150.
- [22] J.K. Mac Kenzie, "Elastic constants of a solid containing spherical holes", *Proceeding Physic Society*, London, Great-Britain, Vol. 63B, No. 1, 1950, pp. 2-11.

- [23] S. Clédat, M. Desmaison-Brut, C. Gault, `` Elastic behaviour of particulate AlN-TiB₂ composites '', *Proceeding of the 9th CIMTEC*, Ed. P. Vincenzini, Florence, Italy, June 1998.
- [24] W. Voigt, *Lehrbuch der Kristallphysik*, Ed. Teubner, Leipzig, Germany, 1928.
- [25] A. Reuss, `` Calculation of the yield point of polycrystals on the basis of the plasticity conditions for single crystals '', *Z. Angew. Math. Mech.*, Vol. 9, No. 1, 1929, pp. 49-58.
- [26] Z. Hashin, S. Shtrikman, `` A variational approach to the theory of the elastic behaviour of multiphase materials '', *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol. 11, 1963, pp. 127-140.
- [27] M. Moriyama, H. Aoki, K. Kamata, `` Mechanical and electrical properties of pressureless sintered TiN-TiB₂ system '', *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.*, Vol. 103, No. 8, 1995, pp. 844-849.
- [28] T. Graziani, C. Melandri, A. Bellosi, `` Fabrication of monolithic TiN and TiN-20 vol % TiB₂ composites '', *J. Hard. Mater.*, Vol. 4, No. 1, 1993, pp. 29-36.